

Planning Comparison for the Capital City Relocation between Brazil and Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This paper background is the decision to move the capital city, this is done by the government to increase efficiency and effectiveness, this could also reduce pressure on the already densely populated capital city. This paper aims to compare plans to move the capital cities of Brazil and Indonesia. The method of this paper is structured literature study. The results of this study indicate that relocating the Brazilian capital has a significant impact on the environmental, political, social, and economic landscape of the country, and has several negative consequences, this should be a lesson for Indonesia, which is in the process of moving the capital. The conclusion of this study is that although there are differences in budget and implementation, Indonesia and Brazil have the same reasons for moving their capital cities and need to pay attention to the impact of moving on environmental aspects and local communities.

KEYWORDS: Capital City, Relocation, Planning

1. INTRODUCTION

Relocating the capital city is a strategic decision that is often taken by the government to increase government efficiency and effectiveness, this also has the effect of reducing pressure on the already densely populated capital city. (Rossman, 2018; Hackbarth & de Vries, 2021), but other research suggests that moving the capital city is not expected to have much impact on improving environmental quality (Hackbarth and Vries, 2021). Relocating the national capital can be a strategy to encourage the development and growth of new regions (Salya, 2022), this strategy includes reducing development disparities between regions, equalizing investment, and infrastructure so as to encourage economic development in new areas (Potts, 1985; Azmy, 2021). Relocating the national capital can be done to reduce pressure on traffic infrastructure and population density in the old capital city (Abubakar *et al.*, 2017), this can occur due to the transfer of the center of government to a new, wider location (Sugiharti *et al.*, 2020).

In some cases, the relocation of the national capital can be triggered by natural disasters or environmental conditions in the old capital that are no longer adequate (Rachmawati *et al.*, 2021; Rahmat *et al.*, 2021). In line with these conditions, moving the capital city can be an opportunity to restore disaster-affected areas and ensure environmental sustainability in the new location. Relocating the national capital can also be carried out with considerations of security and defense, this can be achieved by moving the center of government to a more strategic location in terms of defense or protection, this protection can help improve national security and strengthen the country's defense from external threats (Reva, 2016; Hakim & Infallible, 2022). Relocating the national capital can also be related to symbols and national identity, this is based on the decision to move the capital city as a symbolic statement about the change and progress of the country so that a new national identity emerges (Rossman, 2013; de Vries, 2021).

Indonesia and Brazil are two countries that have experience in planning to relocate capital cities (Mubarq & Solikin, 2019; Moser, 2019). The two countries had relatively the same reasons for moving their capital cities, while the similarities in these reasons existed from territorial centrality to a centralized government system in the capital, this made the city's burden even heavier so that environmental conditions continued to decline (Adinugroho *et al.*, 2022). In terms of the location of the new capital city as well, these two countries moved their capital cities to a location with tropical rainforests around them, even though Indonesia moving to a new island while Brazil did not (de Vries, 2021). Based on the previous explanation, relocating the capital requires careful planning and involves all parties involved in implementing the relocation of the capital to face the challenges that exist. Therefore, this paper aims to review and compare plans to move the capital cities of Brazil and Indonesia.

2. METHOD

This study uses a structured literature review method to compile the existing discussion. Literature review is a critical analysis and evaluation of existing literature on a particular research topic (Paré & Kitsiou, 2017). The aim of a literature review is to provide a

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comprehensive understanding of the current state of knowledge on a particular topic, a literature review can also identify gaps in existing research and highlight potential for future research (Frank & Hatak, 2014).

After identifying and evaluating the existing literature, the researcher then synthesizes the research results to provide an overall picture of the research findings (Randolph, 2019). Randolph (2019) also stated that a literature review often involves grouping studies based on focus, methodology, or results. The next stage is identifying trends or patterns in research. The literature review may also include a discussion of the implications of the research findings, this can lead to a discussion of the limitations of existing research and areas of future research.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Brazil and Indonesia are not the first countries to relocate capital cities. Case studies of relocating capitals have often occurred in various countries, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. List of countries that have moved their capital cities (Hackbarth & de Vries, 2021)

Country	Former Capital	Relocated Capital	Year
Brazil	Rio de Janeiro	Brasília	1956
Mauritania	Saint Louis (Senegal)	Nouakchott	1957
Pakistan	Karachi	Islamabad	1959
Botswana	Mafeking (South Africa)	Gaborone	1961
Libya	Benghazi	Tripoli	1963
Malawi	Zomba	Lilongwe	1965
Belize	Belize City	Belmopan	1970
Tanzania	Dar es Salaam	Dodoma	1973
Nigeria	Lagos	Abuja	1975
Ivory Coast	Abidjan	Yamoussoukro	1983
Germany	Bonn	Berlin	1990
Kazakhstan	Almaty	Nur-Sultan (Astana)	1997
Malaysia	Kuala Lumpur	Putrajaya	2000
South Korea	Seoul	Sejong	2007
Egypt	Cairo	Wedian	Currently built

Brazil decided to move its capital from Rio de Janeiro to Brasilia in 1956 (Hackbarth & de Vries, 2021; Holford, 1962). This decision was taken with the consideration that Rio de Janeiro as the capital city at that time was already very dense and difficult to develop further (Gaffney, 2010). In addition, moving the capital city of Brazil is also seen as one of the efforts to strengthen the unity of the Brazilian nation because Brasilia as a new city built specifically to become the capital does not have a more dominant historical or cultural background compared to other cities in Brazil.

Figure 1. Relocation of the Brazilian capital (Bruton *et al.*, 2015)

In another situation, Indonesia had planned to move the capital city in 1957, President Soekarno initiated the transfer of the national capital to Palangka Raya when he inaugurated the city as the capital of Central Kalimantan, then in 1997 President Soeharto issued Presidential Decree No. 1 of 1997 concerning coordination of regional development. Jonggol as an independent city, this was

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originally intended to be the center of government but was not implemented. In 2013 President Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono put forward a scenario to retain Jakarta as the capital but planned carefully or move the Center of Government out of Jakarta (Ministry of National Development Planning / National Development Planning Agency of the Republic of Indonesia, 2021; Kusno, 2019). However, the plan was ultimately not implemented and Jakarta remained the capital of Indonesia. Finally In 2019, President Joko Widodo announced plans to move the Indonesian capital from Jakarta to the East Kalimantan region. The transfer is expected to become official in 2024 (Yusriyah *et al.*, 2020) and is confirmed by the issuance of Law Number 3 of 2022 concerning the State Capital which has been established on February 15, 2022 as the legal basis for moving the Capital of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia from Jakarta to East Kalimantan.

Figure 2. Capital city of Indonesia Relocation Map (Suprayitno, 2020)

3.1 Lessons Learned from Brasil

The process of moving the capital city from Rio de Janeiro to Brasilia involved building new infrastructure and government buildings in Brasilia which cost a lot of money (Kelly, 2020). The initial stages of construction of Brasilia were carried out relatively quickly due to political pressure to move the National Capital for one period of the President's administration (5 years) starting at the end of 1956 to 1961, which at that time was under the administration of President Juscelino Kubitschek. The location of the new capital city is 600 miles or 934 km west of Rio de Janeiro with an area of: 5,814 km² or 581,400 Ha, and is in the center of the country (De Oliveira, 1997).

The move was considered successful because it succeeded in increasing development in the area around Brasilia and strengthening the unity of the Brazilian nation (Epstein, 1973). The total population of 4.5 million people in 2019 is very much an increase compared to the first transfer of around 136 thousand people in 1960 (Pocketbook for transferring the State Capital, 2021). The highest per capita increase in GDP was in Brazil, namely R\$ 64,653, compared to Rio de Janeiro, only R\$ 31,064. Although relocating the capital was considered successful, the decision to relocate the capital also drew criticism from several parties, especially regarding the cost and environmental impact of building a new city (Holston 1989).

Figure 3. Brasilia as the capital city (Williams, 2005)

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Moving the Brazilian capital from Rio de Janeiro to Brasilia cost Brasilia enormous infrastructure and new government buildings, reaching around IDR 690 trillion (Marcondes, 1959; Mubaroq and Solikin, 2019). This cost includes the construction of roads, bridges, electricity and telephone networks, as well as government buildings, as for the physical form of these buildings such as the parliament building, presidential palace, government offices, and so on. Funding for the initial construction of the Brasilia development uses APBN funds for basic infrastructure and important supporting buildings such as government and employee residences. At the stage of developing a financing scheme, Brazil uses Land Value Capture by selling land in Brasilia while still being supported by the state budget (Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas, 2020).

One of the most significant effects of moving the capital was the transformation of Brasília from a small, backward city into a planned modern city (Epstein, 1973). The city was designed by architect Oscar Niemeyer and city planner Lucio Costa, and its modern architecture and urban design have been recognized as important examples of 20th century urban planning (Naves *et al.*, 2006). The move to the capital has also had a significant impact on Brazil's political landscape. By moving the capital city to the interior of the country, the President of Brazil can promote economic development in the region and reduce the dominance of coastal cities in Brazilian politics (Roett, 1999). The relocation of the capital also helped to decentralize power from the traditional centers of political and economic power in Brazil (Roett, 1999; Beauregard, 2020).

The relocation of the capital also had an impact on the social and cultural aspects of Brazil, it brought together people from different parts of the region and different social backgrounds in the new, modern city. However, the development of Brasilia has also led to the displacement of land belonging to indigenous peoples and other marginalized groups, as well as the destruction of important cultural and historical sites (Holston, 1989; Rawat, 2005). In terms of economic impact, the relocation of the capital had a mixed impact, although it stimulated economic growth and development in the country's interior, it also led to an increase in government spending on infrastructure and services in Brasilia. According to some studies, this confiscated resources from other parts of the country (Quistorff, 2005; Hackbarth & de Vries, 2021).

3.2 Indonesia Current Status

In line with the conditions that have been experienced by Brazil, the proposed relocation of the Indonesian capital has generated a lot of information and perceptions from the public regarding the potential impact on the country's political, social, economic and environmental aspects.

Figure 4. Inauguration of Indonesia's new capital city (Sekertariat Kabinet Republik Indonesia, 2022)

Moving the capital can help decentralize political power in Indonesia, this is because Jakarta is currently the center of political and economic power in the country and moving to a new capital can help transfer that power to other regions (Hadi & Ristawati, 2020). This can also help reduce the risk of political instability in Jakarta which is prone to natural disasters and traffic jams (Farida, 2021). Relocation can also have a significant impact on local communities in new locations (Sutoyo & Almaarif, 2020). New infrastructure developments, such as roads, airports and housing, could bring new economic opportunities to the region. However, it also has the potential to evict local communities and the loss of cultural heritage sites (Sutoyo & Almaarif, 2020; Azhar *et al.*, 2020).

Relocating the capital city can have a positive impact on the Indonesian economy by spurring growth in new areas, one example of a positive economic impact scenario is reducing traffic congestion and air pollution in Jakarta so that it can provide positive economic benefits (Kurnia, 2020). However, relocation will require significant investment, this could cost the state budget a planned

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cost of IDR 690 trillion (Kurnia, 2020; Azmy, 2021). Therefore, economic calculations related to existing valuations need to be prepared and projected for the future.

As the proposed location for the new capital city is in a region that is home to large amounts of rainforest and wildlife, new infrastructure development could negatively impact the environment, causing deforestation, habitat destruction and increased carbon emissions (Teo *et al.*, 2020; Sihombing & Simanungkalit, 2020). The existence of forests on the island of Borneo as the third largest tropical forest in the world after Brazil and the Democratic Republic of the Congo has made Kalimantan known as the lungs of the world, absorbing carbon dioxide, producing oxygen and balancing the global climate (Mutaqin, Muslim, and Rahayu, 2021 in Sabiq *et al.*, 2022). The function of the forest in Kalimantan will undergo drastic changes through the relocation of the National Capital (IKN) which will require forest clearing, large-scale migration of people and the creation of new settlements. The PUPR Ministry will build 5,141 flats, 1,823 special housing units, 101,250 self-help housing units, and 20,500 infrastructure, facilities, and utilities (PSU) units (Patriella, 2022 in Sabiq *et al.*, 2022).

Other literature reports that transport planning in Brasilia is largely the result of its original design for residents who own cars, and limited attention to public transport for those with more limited budgets (Lauriano, 2015), this is slightly different from planning in Indonesia which carries an environmentally friendly theme using mass transportation, but the difference lies in the base of electric vehicles (Ridhani *et al.*, 2021). This difference may be due to the rapid development of electric vehicle technology today.

Based on the various reviews above, both Brazil and Indonesia need large funds to move the capital city, but there are similarities between the two, namely that both Brazil and Indonesia have funding sources from the state treasury and foreign investment (Shatz, 2003; Kodir *et al.*, 2021). As for geographically, both Brazil and Indonesia are relocating to rainforests (Teo *et al.*, 2020: Qiptiyah & Mutiaradevi, 2022), this certainly has an impact on the environment due to clearing and changes to land cover, but the similarity in the location of rainforests has the difference is that Indonesia moved its capital city to a different island, this is due to the location of the island which was previously densely populated and the strategic location of the new capital city (Hasibuan & Aisa, 2020; Mazda, 2022).

The relocation of the National Capital City (IKN) from Jakarta to East Kalimantan has a geographical difference of the island with a very remote location and very different cultures, this will affect the socio-cultural dynamics of the community. This phenomenon has the potential to create social conflict between indigenous people and immigrants as part of multiculturalism. So far, around 83% of socio-economic, political, and cultural activities in East Kalimantan have been dominated by immigrant communities from Javanese, Bugis, Banjar and so on. Meanwhile, 17% are indigenous people who come from the Dayak, Paser, and Kutai tribes (Purnomo & Demartoto, 2022).

The phenomenon of the transfer of new IKNs has an impact on the community's construction of social identity, a threat or the negative impact of expanding the interaction of indigenous people and immigrants can fade the original socio-cultural identity of the people of East Kalimantan (Putri *et al.*, 2019). This allows for conflicts such as claims and competition for cultural quality to the loss of East Kalimantan's socio-cultural identity as an indigenous community in a national and global view (Yuniarti, 2018).

4. CONCLUSION

The relocation of the Brazilian capital has had a significant impact on the country's political, social and economic landscape. Even though it brought significant change, it also had some negative consequences, especially in terms of marginalized communities and the destruction of cultural and historical sites. The potential impacts of relocating the Indonesian capital are complex and far-reaching. While there are potential benefits from displacement, such as decentralization of power and economic growth in new areas, there are also significant risks, including displacement of local people and loss of cultural and environmental heritage.

It is important for the Indonesian government to consider these impacts carefully and develop a plan that addresses these issues. Overall, despite differences in budget and implementation, Indonesia and Brazil share the same reasons for moving their capital cities and must pay attention to the impact of moving on the environment and local communities.

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